

PROSPECTS OF ESTABLISHING AND GROWING SEED OF PASTURE PLANTS IN THE BUKHARA DESERT PASTURE PLANT SEEDING SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION CENTER

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the primary seed production areas of pasture plants established in the years since the establishment of the Scientific Production Center of Bukhara Desert Pasture Nutrient Plant Seed Production and the work done on their organization.*

Keywords: *natural plants, seed production, species, planting agrotechnology, soil, climate, seed production department.*

INTRODUCTION

Bukhara Desert-Pasture Nutritious Plant Seed Breeding Scientific and Production Center (hereinafter referred to as the Center) under the authority of the Silk and Wool Industry Development Committee under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, under the authority of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan It was established on the basis of the decision No. PQ-3603 of March 14, 2018 "On measures for the rapid development of the field of poaching", which defines the structure of the center [1], and this year, degradation of desert pastures primary seed production areas to be established from the number of encountered areas were determined.

In particular, 400 hectares in Jondor primary seed breeding department of Bukhara region, 300 hectares in Gijduvan primary seed breeding department, 150 hectares in Qarovulbazar primary seed breeding department, 150 hectares in Olot primary seed breeding department, For the primary seed breeding department of Forish district of Jizzakh region, 100 hectares, in total, 1100 hectares of pasture land, it was indicated that seed breeding areas will be established.

However, due to the dry climate of Bukhara region in 2018, there was not enough seed stock for planting according to the plan due to the lack of seeds in natural nutritious plants.

In order to eliminate this situation, the management and experts of the center cooperated with the Scientific Research Institute of specialised to karakul pelt and desert ecology of Uzbekistan, located in Samarkand city, and as a result, two programs were established to grow the seeds of nutritious chogon and alabut plants signed bilateral agreements.

According to the agreement, the seeds delivered by the Scientific Research Institute of specialised to karakul pelt and desert ecology were found to be sufficient for 210 hectares of land, and these seeds were distributed to the fields as follows:

- 60 ha from the Gijduvan primary seed production field;
- 57 ha from the Jondor primary seed production field;
- 14 ha from the Karavulbazar primary seed production district;
- 89 hectares of the primary seed production field of Olot district;
- 10 ha to the seed-growing field of Forish District, Jizzakh Region

A total of 210 hectares of degraded desert pastures were planted from November 2018 to the 3rd decade of February 2019.

Pursuant to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2019 [2] "On measures for the comprehensive development of the horticulture industry" No. PQ-4420 343 hectares in the district, 240 hectares in the Gijduvan primary seed-growing department, 136 hectares in the Qorovulbazar primary seed-growing department, 61 hectares in the Olot primary seed-growing department, Forish primary seed-growing department of Jizzakh region 30 hectares in the area, and according to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 7, 2019 "On measures for the rapid development of livestock industries in the Republic of Karakalpakstan" No. 200 hectares of primary seed production department in the Bidaykol massif belonging to "Mulk" ovul citizens' assembly, total: 1010 hectares [3];

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4817 of September 2, 2020 [4], the Takhtakopir branch of the Bukhara Desert-Pasture Nutritious Plant Seed Breeding Research and Production Center was established.

In 2020, 1,000 hectares will be planted in the Gijduvon primary seed breeding department, 1,000 hectares in the Konimekh primary seed breeding department of the Navoi region, 500 hectares in the Karnabota primary seed breeding department of the Samarkand region, and Mubarak primary seed breeding in the Kashkadarya region. 500 hectares in the region, 60 hectares in the Forish primary seed production department of the Jizzakh region, a total of 3060 hectares;

In 2021, a total of 4,100 hectares, of which 1,000 hectares in the primary seed-growing department of Qarovulbazar, Bukhara region, 200 hectares in Farish, Jizzakh region, 500+500 in Guzor and Nishan departments, Kashkadarya region, a total of 1,000 hectares, Navoi region 1,000 hectares of primary seed production units were established in Kyziltepa district, 500 hectares in Karnabota district of Samarkand region, 200 hectares in Kumkurgan district of Surkhandarya region, and 200 hectares in Takhtakopir branch of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In 2022, 1,000 hectares of primary seed cultivation areas were established in Shofirkon district of Bukhara region, 1,000 hectares in Kyziltepa district of Navoi region, 500 hectares in Takhtakopir branch of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and a total of 2,500 hectares in 2022.

In 2023, 500 hectares in Kyziltepa district of Navoi region, 1000 hectares in Konimekh district of Navoi region and 600 hectares in Takhtakopir branch of the Republic of Karakalpakstan were established, in total 2100 hectares in 2023.

To date, the total area of primary seed cultivation is 13000 hectares (Table 1)

Table 1

№	Province name	Name of the primary seed breeding department	Total planted area
1	Takhtakopir district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan	"Mulk" farm is the primary seed breeding department of the Bidaykol massif	1500
2	Bukhara region	Shafirkon District Primary Seed Production Department of Galaba LLC	1000

		Primary seed production department of Amir Temur LLC, Jondor district	400
		Karavulbozor district primary seed breeding department of Karavulbozor specialised to karakul pelt LLC region	1150
		The primary seed breeding department of Kokcha region of Gijduvon district	1300
		Primary seed breeding department of Olot district specialised to karakul pelt LLC region	150
3	Navoi region	Kyziltepa District specialised to karakul pelt Cluster LLC is the primary seed breeding department	2500
		Konimekh district, Sho'rkol massif area, primary seed breeding department	2000
4	Jizzakh region	Forish district Agro-med service LLC Kyzylkum district primary seed production department	300
5	Samarkand region	Primary seed-growing department of Karnab-ota region, Pakhtachi district	500
		Nurabad District, Tutlikorakol Zamini LLC, primary seed breeding department	500
6	Surkhandarya region	Kumkurgan district, Karakul carpet cluster LLC, primary seed production department	200
7	Kashkadarya region	Mubarak district primary seed production department	500
		Nishon district Mirishkor breeding cluster Kensoy massif primary seed breeding department	500
		Guzor district, Kensoy massif, primary seed breeding department	500
	Total		13000

Based on the analysis of the center's employees, it was found that about 20-25% of the pasture areas of the cattle breeding farms located in the desert regions are in crisis.

As a result of this, if we look at the scale of the Bukhara region alone due to climate change, salt and dust particles are rising into the atmosphere with the help of winds and spreading over large areas in a short period of time, as a result of which we are witnessing the emergence of various diseases.

CONCLUSION

In 2023, it was achieved to collect 5 tons of seeds from the seeds of desert pasture nutritious plants from 10,900 hectares of primary seed production areas established in previous years.

Taking into account that the prevention of the above situations, the development of the feed base in the field of cattle breeding, as well as mitigating the consequences of climate change are

one of the main tasks of today, the Center will further expand the area of primary seed production fields for the degraded areas in the pastures and increase the biodiversity of the pastures. In order to increase, in the summer and autumn seasons of 2024, according to the plan for the preparation of seeds of 10 types of desert pasture nutritious plants, the seed stock will be increased to 18 tons, and it will be possible to deliver it to the required farms in the summer and autumn seasons of 2024. In addition, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-24 dated February 16, 2023[5], it is planned to establish 2,000 hectares of primary seed cultivation areas in 2024 and bring the total seed cultivation areas to 15,000 hectares.

REFERENCES

1. Decision PQ-3603 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2018 "On measures for rapid development of the piracy sector";
2. Decision PQ-4420 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2019 "On measures for the comprehensive development of the piracy network";
3. Decision PQ-4512 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 7, 2019 "On measures for rapid development of livestock industries in the Republic of Karakalpakstan";
4. Resolution PQ-4817 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 2, 2020 "On the organization of the activities of the Committee for the Development of Silk and Wool Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan";
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-24 dated February 16, 2023 "On additional measures to ensure the protection and rational use of pastures".